

*PhD Khuraman Karimova**Institute of Folklore ANAS**Leading scientific worker of the department "Dede Gorgud"*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13254459>**ЭПИЧЕСКОЕ МЫШЛЕНИЕ КОРЕИ И АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКИЙ ФОЛЬКЛОР***Хураман Керимова**Кандидат филологических наук**Институт Фольклора Национальной Академии Наук Азербайджана***KOREAN EPIC THOUGHT AND AZERBAIJANI FOLKLORE****Abstract.**

The novel "Princess Bari" by South Korean writer Hwang Sok-Yong is rich in folklore. In the work the real life of ordinary people of the Korean people is reflected and in the life of these people folklore is in harmony with them. In the article the products of folk thinking selected from the work are compared with relevant moments in Azerbaijani folklore, based on these materials, the thinking, mental values and psychology of the peoples of Azerbaijan and Korea belonging to the Altai language family are looked through. During the comparisons the examples of different folklore genres such as beliefs, prohibitions, proverbs, similar situations in some fairy tales, folk expressions used in the language of images, marriage and mourning traditions, folk medicine, the performed rituals protection from the evil forces, etc. are compared.

Аннотация.

Роман южнокорейского писателя Хван Сок Ёна «Принцесса Бари» богат устным народным творчеством. В произведении отражена реальная жизнь простого корейского народа, а фольклор созвучен с жизнью этих людей. В статье выбранные из произведения материалы народной мысли противопоставляются актуальными нюансами азербайджанского фольклора и на основе этих материалов формируются образ мышления, ментальные ценности и психология азербайджанского и корейского народов, принадлежащих к алтайской языковой семье. В ходе сопоставлений сравниваются образцы разных фольклорных жанров: поверья, запреты, пословицы, идентичные ситуации в некоторых сказках, народные выражения, употребляемые в языке образов, свадебные и похоронные обряды, народная медицина, обряды, совершаемые в связи с защитой от злых сил и т.д.

Keywords: *Princess Bari, Korean folklore, Azerbaijani folklore, folk psychology, fairy tale, belief*

Ключевые слова: *принцесса Бари, корейский фольклор, азербайджанский фольклор, народная психология, сказка, поверье.*

Korea is a country with a rich cultural and historical past. This national memory has played an important role as a source in forming their epic thinking. Myths, legends, beliefs, traditions and other folklore examples reflecting national-spiritual values give information from the cultural heritage of Koreans, their way of thinking and living, self-awareness and spiritual development of the people.

During the recent years the activity in the field of literary translation from Korean literature into Azerbaijani has increased significantly. The works by the prominent Korean writers such as "Please, Look After Mom" by Shin Kyung-Sook, "Vegetarian" by Han Kang, "Princess Bari" by Hwang Sok-Yong, "Busy family" by Kang Jong-Yo, as well as "Korean folk tales", which are selections from Korean folklore, have been translated into Azerbaijani. Reading these works a lot of information about the past and present life way, worldview, mental values, psychology, traditions, etc. about the Korean people appears in the thought of the readers. The main point is that there are considerable similarities in the way of thinking of these two peoples, who do not have very close ties and it is seen in moments related to folklore very much.

The novel "Princess Bari" is remarkable in terms of the embodiment of folk and daily life, the work is

rich in folklore elements. The novel reflects the real life of ordinary people. The main character of the work "Princess Bari" is a woman, who until the end fights for her goals and achieves her aims due to the great sacrifices. In addition, there are other bright female images in the work, which influenced the course of events seriously. The mentioned subject was approached from different aspects in the work. One can see similar moments of this diversity, contrasting approach to the theme of women in the work of both peoples.

Proceeding from the work "Princess Bari" we can say that in Korean folklore the women are mainly presented with very strong, skilled, fearless, militant and sometimes cruel features. Woman is a symbol of family. She plays a main role in educating children and protecting the honor of the family. Shamans in Korean mythology are described as beings who protect the position of women, shedding light on their successes. They are the owners of power and force, and the educators in general.

In Azerbaijani folklore women are presented from different perspectives: a woman is a lover, a mother, an educator, at the same time she is a protector of family values and traditions. She is restrained, merciful, devoted, hardworking, patriotic and so on. Sometimes one can also meet the images of cruel, deceitful women.

We observe that in both nations it is more desirable to have a son in the family. In the work “Princess Bari” the woman is exposed to her husband’s stress for the seventh time giving birth to a daughter. Unable to tolerate it, the mother takes her own baby and leaves her alone in the forest. In Azerbaijani folklore the perception of the birth of the next daughter in the family as a tragedy is a familiar psychological picture. In the Azerbaijani folk tale “The unwanted child” we observe a similar plot. Going on a trip the husband warns his wife to cut the head of a baby off and fill her blood into a bottle if she gives a birth to a daughter (Azerbaijani tales, 2005: 349-352). The widespread ritual of the wedding ceremony in Azerbaijan is still alive today: The ritual of belting is performed when the daughter leaves her father’s house as a bride. It is also desirable that more boys were born in the newly-made family in the text said at the ceremony by the groom’s brother by tying a red ribbon around the bride’s waist:

Anam-bacım qız gəlin,

Əl-ayağı düz gəlin.

Yeddi oğul istərəm,

Bircə dənə qız-gəlin. (Karabakh: folklore is also a history, 2014: 139-140)

(Translation: *My dear bride. You are very beautiful and honest. I want you to give a birth to seven sons and a daughter*)

In many Azerbaijani proverbs and sayings, we also observe that the sons are estimated more. For example: “*Have you come a son or a daughter?*”. This is a question that is asked to a person who has gone for an important job in order to find out the result: that is, whether the job has been done or not? Here a son means success, but a daughter means failure. In the proverb “*Daughter’s load is load of salt*” along with moral responsibility, the dowry, given when the daughter leaves her family’s place as a bride, is meant to be a financial problem and so on.

In addition, we can see that the daughter is estimated highly in Azerbaijani folklore. In many folklore texts it is mentioned that the daughter is pretty, helpful, the support of the family in the future, the protector of traditions and a symbol of peace. In the part “The part of Dirse Khan’s son Bughaj Khan” of the epic “The Book of Dede Gorgud”, which reflects the national and moral values of the Azerbaijani people, the words “*Take the man, who has a son, to the white room and the man, who has a daughter to the red room...*” (The Book of Dede Gorgud, 1988: 132) told by Bayandir Khan show that the daughter is very honorable. Here the “red room” is an expression of reverence for the daughter’s father. The sayings such as “*Qızsız ana, duzsuz ana*”; “*Qız qızıl parçası*” (“*A mother without a daughter is a mother without salt*”, “*A daughter is a part of gold*” (AFA, 2004: 290), “*Qız evi – şah evi*” (“*The place of a girl is a king’s palace*”) (Goychay folklore samples, 2022: 286) are also in contrast with the examples that express a negative attitude towards the daughter. From these examples it can be seen that the Azerbaijani people also appreciated the daughter enough. The folk tale “Nazli and her seven brothers” begins so: “*There were seven sons in the family. Unfortunately, these parents did not have a daughter. Their*

sons also want to have a sister” (Nazli and her seven brothers, 1894: 155-219). From this small fragment taken from a tale, it is clear that the birth of a daughter is the most important dream of everyone in the family: parents yearn for a daughter and brothers for a sister.

Throughout history in Korea there has been a belief system called shamanism and this belief is based on the ancestral spirits and other divine beings. Communicating with these spirits the shamans try to heal the sick people, drive away the evil spirits, manage society and do other similar prestigious things. In the work “Princess Bari”, which we are talking about, the author showed the position of shamanism in the life of ordinary Koreans. The main character of the work is Bari. But in the novel there is an image of a shaman-grandmother, who has a special role in the development and disclosure of events, constantly preserves and keeps alive the Korean folk life, traditions, way of thinking and is often mentioned even after her death until the end of the novel. This image is Bari’s grandmother. This woman, who has a special role in the life of her granddaughter, controls the whole life of Bari, whom she perceives as a gift from God, with her mythical force, introduces her to the world of spirits delicately. We get acquainted with the mythical ideas of the people, examples of folklore, information about the worldview through this image. She often tells fairy tales to her granddaughter, performs various rituals, comes to Bari’s sleep after her death, helps and guides her. The shaman grandmother, who is able to call the spirits, talk and control them, teaches them to her granddaughter, too. The tale “Princess Bari”, which was told to her by the grandmother, resembles Azerbaijani fairy tales both in plot and in the course of events. Bari often sees her in a dream much later – even when her grandmother is not alive, and in her dreams her grandmother gives her instructions for her future life. Let’s pay attention at the brief content of one of the dreams given at the end of the work: “*Grandma tells Bari that she needs to find the water of vitality. Bari leaves. At this time, a magpie flies in and helps Bari in all difficult moments. The magpie advises the girl to follow the white path. The old man with a twisted waist, who appeared before Bari, tells the place of the water of vitality. Taking with her palm the girl drinks from the water* (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 279-295). When reading this part of the work several examples of Azerbaijani folklore come to mind. For example, in the folk tale “Malikmammad” the hero falls into a dark world. With the advice of the Emerald bird he goes out into the bright world (Azerbaijan Folklore Collection, 2006: 70-81). Bari also follows the white road in front of her on the advice of a magpie. In the Azerbaijani folk tale “Jirtan”, the children who get lost in the forest in the evening stay at two crossroads: on one side the dog barks, on the other side the light comes: “*Jirtan said: If we go where the dog is barking, maybe it will attack us. Let’s go towards the light*” (Azerbaijani tales, V volume, 2004: 103). Malikmammad calls for help by burning the feather given by the Emerald bird; Bari gets help from the magpie to solve the problems. *The magpie is a harbinger of good news in Azerbaijani folk thinking* (Goychay folklore samples, 2022: 119). The elements such as fire

from the mouth of the dragon, which we see in the work, the magpie brings good news and the protection of castles by evil spirits are also present in Azerbaijani folklore.

In the part given above it is spoken about the water of vitality. There are enough texts about the water of vitality in Azerbaijani fairy tales and legends, in those texts the place of the water of vitality is mainly given by the old men, as in the tale "Princess Bari".

In the novel the author has given a lot of places to the dream interpretations. In the work Bari's reminiscence is given: "*All our family members knew that my grandmother had an extraordinary talent, but only my father did not accept it. Nevertheless, at the end of the year or at the beginning of the New Year, in the early hours of the morning, when he woke up from a terrible dream, he would go to my grandmother alone and interpret his dream*" (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 16). The certain things and events seen in a dream also have their own interpretations in the Azerbaijani folk thinking.

The image of a fairy girl is often observed in Azerbaijani folklore. These fairies with wings are able to fly and get to the space of the mythological hero – to Earth. For example, in the part "The part of Basat's killing Tepegöz" of the epic "The Book of Dede Gorgud" there is a point: There was a famous spring called "The long well". There were fairies in that spring. Suddenly the sheep shuddered. The Shepherd was angry at the sheep in front and went forward. He saw that the fairy girls were tying and flying wing by wing" (The Book of Dede Gorgud, 1988: 196). At the beginning of the novel, Barin's grandmother sees in a dream that a fairy from the sky fell on the roof of their house and she rolled into the courtyard. She clarifies that incident as followings: the fairy made a mistake while watering the flower garden and was punished and thrown to the Earth. At that moment, seven flowers fell in the yard. The fairy took them and handed them to the grandmother. When she wanted to get the rose, the fairy run away. Grandmother ran after her and arrived at the address where her future daughter-in-law lived. She saw a beautiful girl singing in the courtyard (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 17). The grandmother liked the girl and decided that she would marry her son to her. This plot reminds us that in Azerbaijani love epics the hero was given buta in a dream. However, the difference is that it is not the boy who will marry who sees the dream, but his mother. The grandmother offers the girl to become her daughter-in-law and declares that this marriage is a destiny written by God for them. In Azerbaijani folklore, love epics also tell the lover exactly the address of the girl he will marry when she is given "a buta" in a dream. For example, when the hero of the epic "Gurbani" is given a buta, the name and address of his beloved are shown correctly. In response to his father's question, Gurbani says: "Dad, I will go to Ganja. Pari khanim, Ziyad Khan's daughter, was given "a buta" for me (Azerbaijani epics, 2005: 44). In the novel "Princess Bari", as in Azerbaijani love epics, the address of the future bride is reported in a dream.

Let's look through the rituals that exist in both peoples. At the marriage ceremony of her son, "My grandmother finds a long girdle needed to span a child

from somewhere and makes a hoop, passing one of them to my father's foot and the other to my mother's foot" (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 16). The mother ropes her son's leg, tying him to his home or to his family by performing this ritual. This belt is a symbol of unity and family ties. In the Azerbaijani folk language the expressions such as "tying the leg", "shackling the leg" are used as synonyms for the word "to marry". In the part "The part of Ush's elder son Sagrak" of the epic "The Book of Dede Gorgud" Sagrak tells that "I will not return to Galin Oghuz country until I know that my captured brother is dead or alive, or if he is dead, I'll take revenge", when his parents cannot dissuade him from this path they ask Gazan Khan for the advice. At this time, Gazan Khan answers with the following metaphor: "Tie his leg with a horse rope" (The Book of Dede Gorgud, 1962: 91). It can be seen from it that the expression "to rope his leg" and "to shackle", which is said about a boy who is a teenager, is understood in the same sense among the people both in Korea and in Azerbaijan.

In one part of the work Bari recalls such a story about her grandmother: "*Suddenly my grandmother woke up ... and saw her husband's tattered woolen trousers and rabbit fur jacket, which he had taken off before he went to the army, had fallen to the ground. That night, my grandmother ... as she was doing a simple funeral, she performed ancestral rituals and burned my grandfather's clothes*" (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 12-13). The burning of the clothes of the dead, most often the burial, that is, the removal from the house, is one of the mourning customs that existed in Azerbaijan since very ancient times and is still being carried out in modern times (Suleymanova, 2008: 152).

In one part of the novel Bari tells her grandmother that a girl in a white dress came to their yard and said that "*It is not that house*" and returned quickly. Grandmother says: "Now do what I say: spit on the floor three times, then trample it three times with your left foot. ... She is a bedridden nightmare" (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 21-22). Today various rituals are performed by spitting in most regions of Azerbaijan and it is reflected in folklore texts belonging to those regions. The different rituals such as: "*When leaving or starting a business, if a black cat passes in front of you, spit it out three times and then trample it with your foot; spit three times over your shoulder to protect yourself from the evil eyes*" (Goychay folklore samples, 2022: 111) are also carried out nowadays.

In the work we often come across beliefs, prohibitions and trials of Koreans. In the dialogue of the mother-in-law and the daughter-in-law, we see that lying is a sin, a prohibition in folk thinking. Grandmother does not know about the child being thrown into the forest. When she did not see the baby in her place, she persistently asked her daughter-in-law: "Where is my granddaughter?". But the daughter-in-law answered: "I don't know". The grandmother says: "Don't lie, lightning strikes you" (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 6). This text expresses the belief that lying is dangerous, scary, that the owner of a false word will suffer. In Azerbaijani folklore, we can say that, this topic is observed in many

genres. For example, such curses are used: “Let lightning strike you” (Karabakh: folklore is also a history, 2012: 371), “Damn the one who lied” (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore, 2004: 62). In different genres such as proverbs, belief, anecdotes, garavelli, etc. there are many texts on this topic. The examples such as “A liar is Allah’s enemy” and others (Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore, 2002: 218) show clearly the place of lies in the thinking of the people, make it clear that such people are cursed and fall out of trust. In both peoples it is noticed that the one who lied will be subjected to evil, punished by the invisible.

In the work we also meet points related to folk medicine. For example, Bari had a dog named Hyindungi. “Hyindungi moved slowly because it was getting old. Its hair was falling out and its skin was starting to show because the skin disease had spread from its hips to his waist. ... It was necessary to wash the dog with water in which beans had been boiled...” (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 35).

In Azerbaijani folk medicine the boiled bean water is also used for many skin diseases. “It is useful to boil the beans and the water ... can be used against hair loss” (Healing plants, 2021: 63).

Belief in fate and destiny has a strong position in the thinking of the Korean people. For example: *This baby is God’s gift to us; Our Baria is given ability from God; everything is in God’s hands; God is sad because you are hopeless* (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 7; 27; 204; 297). There are corresponding moments in Azerbaijani folklore. The examples such as “*May the hope that Allah gives not be upset*” (The Book of Dede Gorgud, 1988: 51); “*Allah does not give up hope*”, “*Devil is hopeless*” are still used among the people today. In Azerbaijani thinking the prohibitions such as “*Crossing hand you must not stand on foot*” (offended – Kh.K.), “*One must not cry before the sunset* (in the evening - Kh.K.)” (Western Azerbaijan folklore, 2023: 129) and generally all moments that express hopelessness are understood as a protest against Allah.

We see that in both nations, in order to protect themselves from evil forces, everyone imposes certain restrictions and prohibitions on their behavior. Although Bari has not received any information from her husband Ali, who was at war for a long time, she believes that he is alive and well. However, she does not share her thoughts with anyone and explains it so: “*From childhood, I sincerely learned from adults that if I talk about what I want or what I am trying to get, success will go away from me and I will achieve my dream later*” (Hwang Sok-Yong, 2020: 256). Today, there is a belief among the Azerbaijani people that is also useful and that most people believe: “*Foretelling does not bring me success*”. The explanation of this belief collected from Azerbaijan is so: “*When a person talks about his future plans, the devil hears and prevents the realization of this work*”. This kind of approach mentions the sameness in the way of thinking of both peoples.

The similarity of the folklore examples, which we meet in the work “Princess Bari”, with what the Azerbaijani people have been building for thousands of years and sometimes even the same, testifies to the

existence of ties that have united our peoples since the ancient times. From the comparison of beliefs, prohibitions, fairy tales, applause, protection from evil forces, marriage and mourning rituals in the works of both peoples it can be concluded that there are many similarities in the spirituality, way of thinking and approach to life events of the Azerbaijani and Korean peoples.

References

1. **Azərbaycan dastanları.** Tərtib edənlər: M.Təhmasib, Ə.Axundov. Beş cilddə, I c. – Bakı: Lider, 2005, – 392 s. // Azerbaijan epics. Compilers: M.Tahmasib, A.Akhundov. In five volumes, I v. - Baku: Lider, 2005, - 392 p.

2. **Azərbaycan folkloru antologiyası, IX.** Gəncəbasar folkloru. Tərtib edənlər: H.İsmayilov, R.Quliyev. – Bakı: Səda, 2004, – 522 s. // Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. IX. Folklore of Ganjabasar. Compilers: H.Ismayilov, R.Guliyev. - Baku: Sada, 2004, - 522 p.

3. **Azərbaycan folkloru antologiyası, VII.** Qaraqoyunlu folkloru. Tərtib edənlər: H.İsmayilov, Q.Süleymanov. – Bakı: Səda, 2002, – 464 s. // Anthology of Azerbaijani folklore. VII. Folklore of Garagoyunlu. Compilers: H.Ismayilov, G.Suleymanov. - Baku: Sada, 2002, - 464 p.

4. **Azərbaycan folkloru külliyyatı, I c.** Tərtib edənlər: H.İsmayilov, O.Əliyev. – Bakı: Səda, 2006, – 400 s. // Azerbaijan Folklore Collection. I v. Compilers: H.Ismayilov, O.Aliyev. - Baku: Sada, 2006, - 400 p.

5. **Azərbaycan nağılları, 5 cildə, I c.,** Tərtib edən: H.Zeynallı. – Bakı: Şərq-Qərb, 2005, – 360 s. // Azerbaijani tales. in 5 volumes, I v., Compiled by: H.Zeynallı. - Baku: East-West, 2005, - 360 p.

6. **Azərbaycan nağılları, 5 cildə, V c.** Tərtib edənlər: Ə.Cəfərli, S.Əhlimanqızı. – Bakı: Çıraq, 2004, – 336 s. // Azerbaijani tales. in 5 volumes, V v. Compilers: A.Jafarli, S.Ahlimangizi. - Baku: Chirag, 2004, - 336 p.

7. **Göyçay folklor örnəkləri.** Tərtib edənlər: X.Kərimov və b. – Bakı: Elm və təhsil, 2022, – 296 s. // Goychay folklore examples. Compilers: Kh.Karimova and others. - Baku: Science and education, 2022, - 296 p.

8. **Hvanq Sok Yonq.** Şahzadə Bari. Tərcüməçilər: K.Kamilzadə, R.Babazadə. – TEAS Press Nəşriyyat evi, 2020, – 308 s. // Hwang Sok-Yong. Princess Bari. Translators: K.Kamilzade, R.Babazade. - Publishing house TEAS Press, 2020, - 308 p.

9. **Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud.** Tərtib edənlər: F.Zeynalov, S.Əlizadə. – Bakı: Yazıçı, 1988, – 265 s. // The Book of Dede Gorgud. Compilers: F.Zeynalov, S.Alizade. - Baku: Yazichi, 1988, - 265 p.

10. **Qarabağ: folklor da bir tarixdir.** III c. Tərtib edən: İ.Rüstəmzadə. – Bakı, Elm və təhsil, 2012, – 468 s. // Karabakh: folklore is also a history. III v. Compiler: I.Rustamzade. - Baku, Science and education, 2012, - 468 p.

11. **Qarabağ: folklor da bir tarixdir.** VII c., Tərtib edən: L.Vaqıfçı (Süleymanova). – Bakı: Zərdabi LTD, 2014, – 444 s. // Karabakh: folklore is also a history. VII v., Compiler: LVagifgizi (Suleymanova) - Baku: Zardabi LTD, 2014, - 444 p.

12. **Qərbi Azərbaycan folkloru**, I c. Tərtib edən: L.Vaqıfızı (Süleymanova). – Bakı: Elm və təhsil, 2023, – 400 s. // Western Azerbaijan folklore. I v. Compiler: LVagifgizi (Suleymanova) - Baku: Science and education, 2023, - 400 p.

13. **Süleymanova L.** Şəkidə yas adətləri // Dədə Qorqud. Elmi-ədəbi toplu, – Bakı: 2008, №4 (29), Nurlan, s. 146-152. // Suleymanova L. Mourning customs in Sheki // Dede Gorgud. Scientific-literary collection, - Baku: 2008, №4 (29), Nurlan, p. 146-152.

14. **Şəfali bitkilər**, Tərtib edənlər: İ.Məcidi, O.Bayramlı. –Bakı: Universal Nəşriyyat və Çap Evi, 2021, – 533 s. // Healing plants. Compilers: I.Majidli, O.Bayramli. - Baku: Universal Publishing and Printing House, 2021, - 533 p.

15. **Nazlı və onun yeddi qardaşı(nağıl)** // Сборник материалов для описания местностей и племен Кавказа. Вып. XIX. Тифлис, 1894. II отдел, с.155-219 // Nazli and her seven brothers (tale) // Collection of materials for the description of the localities and tribes of the Caucasus. Issue XIX. Tiflis, 1894. II Department, p.155-219

16. **Книга моего деда Коркуда**. Огузский героический эпос. Перевод академика В.В.Бартольда. Издательство М-Л. СССР, 1962, –301 с. // The Book of Dede Gorgud. The Oghuz heroic epic. Translated by Academician V.V. Bartold. Publishing house M-L. USSR, 1962, - 301 p.

Samples, the source of which is not specified, were collected by us and are in our personal archive.